

*Research Paper***ASSESSMENT OF VULNERABILITY TO FIRE HAZARD
OF RDA MARKET IN RAJSHAHI CITY**

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Abstract

A fire hazard has been a very frequent occurrence in an urban area, nowadays. When urban areas are built without following any guidelines it becomes unmanageable. In Rajshahi city, the RDA market is established, in violation of BNBC (Bangladesh National Building Code) rules and regulations and without proper fire safety measures. Recently, a massive fire was caught at the factory of Kemiko Pharmaceuticals Limited in Rajshahi city. The study attempted to analyze the vulnerability level in the RDA market. Also, 40 individual shops are surveyed to check individual assessments. Analysis based on this indicator was performed and indicators were selected for analysis. To calculate the vulnerability, the indicators were weighted (depending on importance) and graded (based on condition). The findings show that the market building is highly vulnerable with practically no fire safety measures. To reduce vulnerability, there needs to be some proper fire safety planning, market design and modification with the assistance of expert personnel, following appropriate rules and policies.

Keywords

Fire hazard, BNBC, Vulnerability, Fire safety, Expert personnel.

1. Introduction

Fire hazard risk has become a major concern in Bangladesh, as several major fires have occurred in recent years (Rahman, 2014). With the growing

population and rapid urbanization, unplanned housing and congestion in both residential and commercial areas are increasing with accelerates the risk of fire hazard (Opie et al., 2014, Ahmed & Sakib, 2022). Given the various measures, rules and regulations that have been introduced in recent decades, there are still several fire outbreak accidents that result in significant losses of lives, livelihoods, equipment and property (Uddin & Hossain, 2009). From the beginning of 1997 to end of 2018, around 250,000 fire incidents occurred in Bangladesh (Sakib et al., 2020). Although the Rajshahi region is not much developed economically and industrially, due to unplanned commercial structure or other aspects there are also some fire hazard scenarios (Poddar & Shanta, 2017). Rajshahi Development Authority market (RDA) has recently been identified by Fire Service & Self Defense as being the most vulnerable to fire risk (Daily Star, 2019). But the market authority has not taken any steps to improve its condition.

Fire hazard is one such phenomenon that currently frequently causes enormous economic loss as well as the tragedy of human death. If there look into the examples, we can see that the reported incidences of fire in Bangladesh between 2004 and 2006 were 7140, 7135 and 9642, respectively. In addition to human death and injury, property damage in Dhaka city was reported to be more than Tk. 6 Crore on average each year due to fire incidents (Sayeeduzzaman, 1990). Also, this number could be applicable anytime in Rajshahi city if effective measures are not taken. RDA market, Rajshahi City's most popular shopping mall, is situated in Shaheb Bazar (Rajshahi Central Business District) in Rajshahi. A three-story building together with a newly built building covers an area of 2.18 acres. The area is a commercial area and a lot of restaurants, shopping malls and many other shops are surrounded by the market. The narrow access road, the insufficient body of water, and neglect of rules and regulation during building construction exacerbate the vulnerability of fire hazard on the market. If any fire hazard happens at this shopping mall, it will also affect the surrounding area. That's why the study was conducted for its improvement to attain the existing condition of this fire risk area. From the city planning perspective in Bangladesh, the fire safety issue in large urban areas, including Rajshahi, is not strongly emphasized. In most cases, the issue of community protection is widely debated by local newspapers immediately after any large-scale fire devastation but over time, the issue eventually falls away from people's minds. Currently, this metropolitan city's authority has no contingency plan and adequate preparedness to prevent large-scale fire disorders. Unfortunately, very little research has been conducted on fire protection in city markets in Bangladesh. So, the current research focuses on the assessment of fire risk of the RDA market in Rajshahi and analyzes the vulnerable level of the fire hazard of this building. After risk assessment, there take some safety precautions. If fire prevention or mitigation is more feasible

for the RDA market may be debatable, but there is no question the matter should be considered in the RDA market's planning.

2. Methodology

The primary data was collected in this study from a field survey & physical survey conducted on the RDA sector, and the secondary data was collected from Rajshahi Development Authority, newspapers, journals and various websites. Possible vulnerable zones had been selected by following different factors of BNBC-2006 guideline considerations like emergency departure matters, fire prevention and extinguishing systems, electrical systems etc.

2.1. Fire Risk Assessment Methods

Risk indexing is a way to evaluate various attributes into a single value, and the number and types of parameters (attributes) considered and the numerical functions used to summarize these parameters vary mainly in different risk indexes. The most famous among different types of fire risk ratings are Gretener's index, FRAME index, Dow's fire and explosion index, fire system assessment system index and hierarchical approach (Šakenaite & Vaidogas, 2010). In most of these indexes, the criteria are grouped into different categories describing different aspects of fire safety, such as fire prevention, egress, compartmentalization, detection and warning, emergency response etc.

To evaluate the FRI for the soft parameters, we adopted a linear additive model of the form below for the current work:

$$FRI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad (1)$$

Where x_i was a dimensionless score or grade points for parameter i , w_i was the importance of parameter i and n was the number of total parameters. The weight w_i was used to integrate the differences in the value of the parameters relative to each other and was usually calculated, if available, by expert opinion and/or from past data. The grade points or scores x_i indicate the 'measurement' of the danger, outcome or protection given by a parameter i . Since the units of measurement were different for different parameters, x_i was expressed as a standardized dimensionless number, so that they could be added together (Watts & Kaplan, 2001). This FRI could be easily included in developing a much broader FRI involving other categories of 'hard' parameters as long as the relative importance of soft and hard parameters could be established.

2.2. Development of the Parameters and Weights

In general, the shop will follow the fire safety legislation set by BNBC-93 as well as the BFSCDA regulations for the 'strong' parameters.

Although there are some soft criteria in the BFSCDA checklist, they're not detailed. There is also no other standard set by any regulatory authority to ensure operating protection and fire management practices in the market (although in some cases, additional rules and checks are set by the purchasing foreign firm). The soft parameters were initially selected using BFSCDA's checklist, literature review and discussion with two fire safety experts. A pilot survey was then carried out at the market to ensure that the identified parameters are 'measurable' during inspections and the parameters are fine-tuned to produce the final list of 20 (i.e., $n = 20$) soft parameters. The weight, W_i of equation 1 may represent a variety of factors that explain 'importance', but the comparison of these important factors may be more difficult. The weight represents the significance of the parameters in terms of potential impacts for this study. This is if an expert determines that deficiencies in this parameter will cause high harm to both life and products, while the weight is minimum-1, if the predicted damage is small, a soft parameter will be given the maximum weight, 5. To prevent a disparity in interpretation among the experts about the 'measure' of value (Dodd & Donegan, 1994) experts were presented with a weighting scheme to direct their ranking, see Table 1.

Ten experts were then presented with the list of the soft parameters and the weighting scheme. These specialists were selected from the researchers and the practitioners directly involved in the management of fire safety or disasters. These include four academics involved in the design of buildings for disaster management and fire safety, three BFSCDA officers, one Bangladesh Army official responsible for fire protection, a National Housing Authority engineer and an urban risk reduction specialist from the Comprehensive Disaster Management Programme. Using their judgment of the parameters and their importance, the experts provided their grades for the selected soft parameters as per Table 1.

Advanced techniques such as analytical hierarchy, fuzzy theory, reliability interval system, grey relational model or simulation approaches have been applied in the literature to generate

Table 1: Definition of Weights for Each Parameter

Weight	Description of Consequences
5	Most important (if not present, very high damage to both life and properties may occur.)
4	Important (if not present, considerable damage to both life and properties may occur.)
3	Essential (loss of life may not occur but other losses and injuries are

	high)
2	Essential (loss of properties and injuries are considerable)
1	Not essential but preferable.

Source: Assessment of Fire Risk in the Readymade Garment Industry (Industry, 2014)

accurate parameter weights Judgments from experts (Ming Lo, 1999; Lo et al., 2005; Zhao, 2004). Nonetheless, given the lack of resources to produce these tests, and remembering Watt's 1991 third fire risk axiom — there is no purely objective or empirical way to measure fire risk — we follow the simple procedure of averaging the weights for each parameter. To ensure that the weights are not significantly influenced by the extreme values provided by one or two experts, the maximum and minimum weights for each parameter are omitted and the remaining eight experts average the weights. Table 2 describes the list of expert opinions on the soft parameters and their corresponding weights.

Table 2: Weight of the Parameters

Rank	Parameters short name	Parameters description	Weight average
1	Exit door	Locked/unlocked condition of the exit door	5.00
2	Chemicals	Existence of chemical material inside	4.75
3	Block furniture	Blockade of exit corridor by furniture/other material	4.75
4	Fire drill	The practice of fire drill	4.63
5	Extinguisher workability	Serviceability of fire extinguisher	4.63
6	Water in tank	Presence of adequate water in the tank	4.50
7	Extinguisher operator	Performance of fire extinguisher operator	4.38
8	Exposed utility inside	Exposed electric or gas line inside the factory floor	4.25
9	Fire pump access	Accessibility to the fire hydrant	4.25
10	Switchboard	Location of main electric switchboard	4.13

11	Communication	Communication between command centre to floor	4.13
12	Fire pump protection	Protection of fire pump against mechanical damage	4.00
13	Occupant load	Number of workers/occupants per unit floor area	3.88
14	Roof access	Unobstructed access to the roof	3.88
15	On roof obstruction	Presence of obstruction on the roof	3.75
16	Emergency light	Serviceability/working condition of emergency lights	3.75
17	Electric overhead	Existence of electric overhead line in front of the building	3.63
18	Alternate power	Presence of alternative power system	3.63
19	First aid	Availability of first aid kits on the shop floor	3.50
20	Gas mask	Availability of gas mask for emergencies	3.38

Source: Assessment of Fire Risk in the Readymade Garment Industry (Industry, 2014)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Existing Condition

In front of the RDA market, the road was approximately 20 feet wide. There was a 10-foot-wide road to the east, west and south portion of the market. But there was not enough wide road in front of the market for fire truck parking.

There were two three-storied buildings on the RDA market. The old one with a wide entrance was unplanned and built to have two stories but additional floors had been added later (Daily Star, 2019). There was no such fire extinguishing device listed in 'Ogni Nirbapon Bidhi O Nitimala 2014' (Auto Fire Extinguisher, Sprinkler System, Water Reservoir, Fire Hydrant, Emergency Exit etc.) on the RDA market except some manual fire extinguishers. This research there surveyed 40 shops in the RDA market to ensure whether these shops were capable enough to protect themselves from any fire hazards or not. It was quite unfortunate that only 7 shops had a fire license from Bangladesh

Fire Service and Civil Defense. i.e., these 7 shops were capable to protect their shop from any vulnerable situation of fire hazard.

3.2. Causes for Fire Vulnerability

In the RDA market, there were many dangerous things which were the causes of any fire hazard in the market. Some major causes of these were- electric short, loose wiring, overheating of used electric shorts, electric kettle, smoking unconsciously. Also, sometimes unplanned smoke and heat could be spread to the market and the main causes were the service duct (electric and other cables such as- Network telephones etc). If any unwanted flames were created in the market, the existing interior decoration had a large amount of flammable material and would quickly spread. In the market, there was the possibility of people being trapped inside and not having any emergency power supply.

Table 3: Existing fire prevention and extinguishing systems

No.	Indicator	Existence
1	Exit door	To exit the market- at the bottom of the market, there were 3 roads to the east, 9 roads to the west and the main road to the north. There was a total of 7 stairs to the second and third floors of the market, these were 4 feet wide.
2	Block furniture	Yes
3	Fire drill	No
4	Extinguisher workability	Yes
5	Water reservoir	There was no water reserve anywhere in the market
6	Extinguisher operator	Yes
7	Exposed utility inside	Yes
8	Fire pump access	No
9	Switchboard	Danger
10	Communication	No
11	Fire pump protection	No
12	Occupant load	Medium
13	Roof access	No
14	Emergency light	No
15	Electric overhead	Yes

16	Alternate power	Yes
17	First aid	No

Source: Authors Survey, 2021

There used the FRI tool to calculate whether the RDA market shops were safe or not. As chemical, gas mask and on roof obstruction is not applicable for the market, those three parameters were omitted from the calculation. For the calculation there uses the existence of different indicators. Here the safe parameter was assumed to be 1.00 value and the risk parameter was assumed to be 5.00 value. Then the value obtained by the calculation had been verified in numbers between 1-5, where value 1 counted as the safest position and value 5 counted as the riskiest zone. There got a value by calculation 3.36 which was more than 3. Therefore, from the calculation, it was clear that all these shops of RDA markets were at High risk. The loss of life may not occur there but other losses and injuries will be high.

4. Conclusion

This research shows the very weak fire prevention system of the RDA market. There was no fire safety plan in favor of the market. A fire safety plan needs to be prepared for the market on an emergency basis and subjects to the approval of the Fire Service and Civil Defense Directorate, the next step must be implemented. Fire service and civil defense department numbers had not been placed in any market place. The national Help Desk number, 999 and the telephone number of the Rajshahi Sadar fire station, nearest to the building, should be kept in large and clear form, with visible and multiple locations in the building. There was no training from the manpower fire service and civil defense working in the market. Training in firefighting, rescue and first aid should receive by the Fire Service and Civil Defense Department. The public address system should be established in the market. Smoking inside the building should be banned. Formed a Fire Safety Cell for the market, a trained fire extinguisher, rescue and first aid, with 20 members, working in the market under the supervision of 01 responsible officers trained in the cell. The task of this group will be assisting people in safety evacuating from the market by disaster, to rescue people who are trapped or unable to evacuate, and to engage in rapid-fire extinguishers with fire extinguishers on the market. The staff of this team should be trained in firefighting and rescue. The staff of this team will ensure proper maintenance and effectiveness of the fire protection system installed in the market. The auto-shutdown switch should be kept on every floor so that the power line can be switched off in the event of a fire or any emergency. After all, the RDA market is very risky, so it was recommended to break the market and re-establish the modern firefighting system.

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